

On two implicit issues in prediction modeling of landslide susceptibility

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Abstract—this contribution argues the interpretation of prediction-rate curves of landslide susceptibility and the corresponding prediction-pattern uncertainties. The focus is on two main issues in any kind of spatial prediction modeling: (1) isolating the meaningful parts of prediction-rate curves from a cost-benefit point of view and (2) comparing the qualities of prediction patterns obtained by different mathematical models and/or dissimilar spatial evidences. Mathematical models, methods, and databases generated prediction maps (we prefer the term prediction patterns) hard to evaluate due to inevitable relativity of measures, representations and confidence. This is a major problem, with modelling assumptions and justifications mostly ignored or poorly discussed. We consider prediction-rate curves, obtained by cross-validation, as standardized procedure. The curves are the result of cross-validating prediction patterns with the distribution of occurrences more recent than the ones used to generate the patterns. The two issues concern all types of modeling independently of algorithmic complexity or database formats. We examine an application example and its analytical strategy to point at resolving problems of pattern evaluation, comparison and uncertainty measure. The need becomes evident of collaborative efforts towards solutions analyzing a common multi-format database.

Keywords— prediction-rate curves, prediction pattern, landslide susceptibility, cross validation, uncertainty

I. INTRODUCTION

This contribution argues the interpretation of prediction-rate curves and the corresponding prediction-pattern uncertainties.

During the past four decades, with the increasing availability of spatially distributed data, an army of numerical applications attempted predicting the likely locations of future landslide

occurrences. Researches in selected study areas captured past evidential settings at the location of known occurrences to recognize the distribution of future ones. Mathematical models, methods, and databases generated prediction maps that were hard to evaluate and compare due to the inevitable relativity of measures, representations and confidence [1]. This is a major problem, with modelling assumptions and justifications mostly ignored or poorly discussed.

Wide use has been made of the Receiving Operator Characteristic curve, ROC, to assess and compare the validity of binary classifiers and their discrimination thresholds. An example is the identification of the proportion of occurrences captured by cumulative proportions of the study area by using a point of significant inflection where the slope of the curve changes from steep to gentle [2]. However, it is debatable whether it is a reliable tool for comparisons. Instances of ROC curves generated by different mathematical models could have equal area under the curve, AUC, but different curve shapes with corresponding dissimilar prediction patterns of landslide susceptibility. Such curves appear unable to compare the patterns satisfactorily and to reveal their uncertainty. In particular, the AUC value of the ROC curve itself represents just an indicator of general reliability [3].

McClish [4] considers interpretation and comparison of the ROC curves when interests do not lie in the entire range of rates and suggests evaluating the area under a portion of the curve or under a specific point of the curve. Furthermore, Dodd and Pepe [5] propose an estimator to interpret a partial area under the ROC curve. They point at costs and benefits associated with the curve rates and corresponding choices. Chung and Fabbri [6] recommend the ratio-of-effectiveness for rate intervals that satisfy monotonically decreasing tangents (slopes) of the curve. That is to

contrast them from the slope of random distribution and isolate the corresponding parts of the prediction pattern.

The focus here is on two main issues: (1) isolating the meaningful parts of prediction-rate curves from a cost/benefit point of view and (2) comparing the qualities of prediction patterns obtained by different mathematical models and/or dissimilar spatial evidences. These are very general critical requirements in spatial prediction modeling. The next section defines the concepts related with the issues and is followed by a section on application examples. The last section provides some suggestive solutions and complex questions related to the two issues in spatial prediction modeling.

II. PREDICTION PATTERNS, PREDICTION-RATE CURVES, AND CROSS-VALIDATION

The term “prediction pattern” indicates the spatial configuration of the prediction rates when converted into equal-area ranks. This is why we do not use the term prediction map. Mathematical models integrate spatial relationships into “likelihood” of landslide occurrence, the prediction rates [6]. A prediction-rate curve is a graphical representation of ordered equal-area ranks of prediction rates.

We propose an interpretation of prediction-rate curves, obtained by cross-validation, as a convenient standardized procedure for any modeling. The curve is the result of cross-validation of a prediction pattern with the distribution of occurrences more recent than the ones used to generate the pattern [7]. The very process leads to estimating pattern uncertainty [8]. The following section provides examples of patterns, curves and comparisons.

III. EXAMPLES OF APPLICATIONS

The examples used here of prediction-rate curves, from prediction patterns of landslide susceptibility, derive from the works on Lake Albano, a volcanic crater 20 Km south of the metropolitan city of Rome, in Italy [9].

Mass movements of various dynamic types affect the inner slopes of the crater. They are either sub-aerial or sub-aqueous. Seismicity, uplifting and gas exhalations of H₂S and CO₂ make the lake a multi-hazard site. The gases might have contributed to the flood in 398 BC. Fig. 1 shows the distribution of 120 subaerial linear (blue) and 29 polygonal (red) landslide forms. No information is available on the temporal sequence of the mass movements. We grouped dynamic types of landslides due to the closeness of their settings. We used a 5m-resolution raster database, of 1002x1202 pixels, constructed for susceptibility studies, which implied a variety of assumptions [9]. The study area excluding the lake itself covers 975,093 pixels of which 9,379 indicate the location of the subaerial landslides. We

assumed that the remainder of the study area indicates the locations without known landslides. The database contained eight raster images of the settings as follows: land use, **u**, lithology, **l**, categorical, and six continuous fields extracted from high-resolution digital elevation points, aspect, **a**, digital terrain model, **d**, slope, **s**, curvature, **c**, planform, **f** and profile, **p**.

We converted the images into spatial evidence of landslide presence or absence in support of modeling susceptibility as likelihood ratios then integrated into prediction patterns by mathematical models. For all the patterns, we grouped the sorted ratios from 200 equal area ranks into 14 classes as shown in the legend: narrower classes for higher ranks. Each rank has approximately 4875 pixels (i.e. 0.5% of study area).

Figure 1. Over the hill-shaded relief are the 120 linear and 29 polygonal subaerial forms in the Lake Albano study area.

Fig. 2 shows the prediction pattern obtained using the 120 subaerial linear forms, the eight images of the settings and the Empirical Likelihood Ratio function, ELR. Fig. 3 shows the prediction pattern using the higher 15% of 29 subaerial polygonal forms and a Logistic Discriminant Function, LOG. Ranks with different models and forms are thus comparable.

The diagram in Fig. 4 compares the prediction-rate curves for both the subaerial forms using the two modelling functions. Sequential exclusion of four occurrences for the 120 and of one for the 29 forms generated iterative cross-validations. The curves captured the prediction rates at the locations of the excluded occurrences in each partial prediction pattern obtained using the remaining occurrences. The ELR and LOG curves in Fig. 4 for the linear forms are very steep and almost coinciding. An inflexion point occurs at the top 4.2% ranks of study area corresponding to the 60% of the 120 occurrences. A sharper inflexion point for the polygonal form curves occurs at the top 8.5% rank of the study area with the 58% of the 29 occurrences.

Figure 2. ELR prediction pattern of the 120 linear forms (6440 pixels).

Figure 3. LOG prediction pattern of the 29 polygonal forms (2939 pixels).

Using the ratio of effectiveness [6] in Fig 4, the top 12% classes of the red curve for the 120 linear and the top 8% classes of the broken blue curve for the 29 polygonal forms are acceptable from a cost/benefit point of view. The remainder of the curves show no benefit. We could use all the techniques cited in the introduction to threshold critical ranges of ranks or proportions.

The curves compare the predictive quality of different models and different forms in terms of “likelihood” of the next four linear or next polygonal occurrences, respectively. Each model uses a particular type of normalization and combination rules for integrating the spatial evidence. We can interpret the original incommensurable prediction rates only as equal-area ranks.

Furthermore, we can take the set of partial prediction patterns from the iterative process of sequential exclusion and compute some revealing statistic on them. Out of the 29 iterations for the polygonal form LOG curve, shown as blue broken line in Fig. 4,

we have computed a “Target pattern” with the median rank of the 29 for each pixel and then an “Uncertainty pattern” ranking the ranges around the median. Fig. 5 shows the LOG Uncertainty pattern for the 29 polygonal forms.

Figure 4. ELR and LOG prediction-rate curves for linear and polygonal terrestrial (subaerial) forms. The top 8 to 12% ranks are of concern as indicated by the bars on the lower left; lower ranks show relatively higher uncertainty.

Figure 5. LOG Uncertainty pattern of the 29 polygonal forms.

Here low values are more important than high values. The Target pattern, not shown here, appears indistinguishable from the prediction pattern in Fig. 3. However, it allows us to measure the associated relative uncertainty. Clearly, we have a relationship between the prediction-rate curve and the Uncertainty pattern. Comparing the pattern in Figure 3 with the one in Fig. 5, we can see that higher prediction ranks (colors from red to purple) correspond to lower uncertainty ranks (light blue to dark blue colors). Intermediate and low prediction ranks show relatively higher uncertainties. Other studies using a variety of prediction models confirm the presence of higher uncertainties for intermediate ranks with respect to the two extremes of highest and lowest ranks [8].

IV. RESOLVING THE ISSUES

We have described a basic modelling strategy that implies a baseline stepwise approach of a very general nature. **Firstly**, we capture spatial relationships between landslide occurrences and their spatial context in the study area: for instance using an empirical likelihood ratio, ELR, to measure the contrast between settings of presence of occurrences and settings of presumed absence. **Secondly**, we integrate the likelihood ratios of all the pieces of spatial evidence using an ELR function (or an LOG function or some other function) with its combination rules. **Thirdly**, we group the occurrences into older and presumed younger ones and use the older ones to generate a prediction pattern for the younger ones: cross-validation captures the prediction rate for each occurrence to construct the prediction-rate curve for interpretation in addition to providing a set of partial prediction patterns. **Fourthly**, we compute Target and Uncertainty patterns by rank-based statistics (for instance computing median and range or some other statistics): we can threshold the Uncertainty pattern at tentatively lower levels to show only the corresponding ranks of the initial prediction pattern (or of the Target pattern) for geomorphologic interpretation.

The two issues concern all types of modeling independently of the algorithmic complexity or database format. Two examples are raster-based and vector-based modeling, with either pixels or slope units as indicators of landslide occurrences and of their physical context as spatial evidence. This also applies to other tabular database formats.

Besides answering the obvious questions, “Where is the square kilometer with the highest susceptibility and is at least 10 m from the known occurrences?” or “Can we do any better with our database and study area?” We can consider now a multitude of complex questions with many answers like the following ones.

- Are slope-unit based prediction patterns preferable to the raster-based ones?
- For modeling, should we select the remainder of the study area as non-occurrence locations or chose randomly as many locations as those of the occurrences?
- What part of the prediction pattern is of relevance for generating susceptibility classes of practical utility?
- How should we compute and threshold the Uncertainty patterns? Which Statistics?
- If we know or suspect spatial evidence being conditionally dependent, how severely would it disturb the prediction pattern?
- Would sophisticated modeling functions, such as Random Forest or Artificial Neural Networks, generate preferable results to justify their use? Would a simpler modeled prediction pattern be as good or help in their interpretation?

The application examples with their analytical strategies and corresponding assumptions point at unresolved problems and at some solutions out of many. The key point for comparison of prediction patterns is to keep all selections fixed, whatever they are: equal-area ranks, etc. Given the implicit complexity of the two issues, the need becomes evident of collaborative efforts ideally analyzing a common raster-and-polygon database: as recommended in [7], further motivated in [8] or attempted in [10] with a slope-unit based benchmark dataset.

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